

Stability of Essential Oils in Pang-Rum by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry

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Abstract—Ancient Thai perfumed powder was used as a fragrance for clothing, food, and the body. Plant-based natural Thai perfume products are known as Pang-Rum. The objective of this study was to evaluate the stability of essential oils after six months of incubation. The chemical compositions were determined by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), in terms of the qualitative composition of the isolated essential oil. The isolation of the essential oil of natural products by incubate sample for 5 min at 40 °C is described. The volatile components were identified by percentage of total peak areas comparing their retention times of GC chromatograph with NIST mass spectral library. The results show no significant difference in the seven chromatograms of perfumed powder (Pang-Rum) both with binder and without binder. Further identification was done by GC-MS. Some components of Pang-Rum with/without binder were changed by temperature and time.

Keywords—GC-MS analysis, essential oils, stability, Pang-Rum.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN ancient Thai society, the use of incense is traditional or ceremonial; it has been part of Thai society for a long time. There are many kinds of fragrances such as scented water, perfumed water, perfumed powder, marl powder, etc., but the most commonly used were perfumed water (Nam-Ob) and perfumed powder (Pang-Rum). Natural Thai perfume were divided two type; animal [1] or plant-based. Those oils derived from animals include four types of substance suitable for use in perfumes such as ambergris, castoreum, civet, and musk, while from plants are used the flowers, seed, bark, resin, and gum of plants [2].

Pang-Rum is a Thai perfumed powder used as a natural cosmetic since ancient times for the face and skin. It is made from different parts of plants and various plants. Pang-Rum was composed of white clay filler and floral water. Floral water was prepared from aromatic plants such as *Aquilaria crasna* Pierre, *Alyxia nitens* Kerr, and *Pandanus amaryllifolius* Roxb. [3]. Both the white clay filler and floral water is made by smoked incense; is composed of Frankincense, peel of Bergamot, white sugar and brown sugar. Normally, the physical and chemical stability of the fragrance can change the compounds when stored over a long period of time, by light and by temperature.

The aim of this research was the study of the aromatic chemical compounds in Pang-Rum and to compare it with

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Pang-Rum with binder for stability in different temperatures and for a period of zero days, one month, three months, and six months.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Preparation of Samples [4]

Samples were prepared into two formulations. One was Pang-Rum (F1) without binder and another one was Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder solution (binder is corn starch) (F2). The samples were then weighed into silicone molds of about 10 grams per specimen in each 2.5 x 2.5 cm² mold. Finally, the samples were dried by free evaporation. The samples were then sealed and stored until analysis. The preparation process is described in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Process of preparation of the sample

B. Stability of Essential Oil

All samples were kept in a sealed package. The samples were stored at different temperatures (room temperature and 45°C) for one, three, and six months. The samples were analyzed at zero days, and one, three, and six months by GC-MS.

C. Essential Oil Analysis

For testing, a one gram sample was analyzed using a GC sampler 80, 7890A GC system, and 5975C inert XL MSD with a Triple-Axis detector, all made by Agilent Technologies Ltd.

GC-MS conditions [5], [6]

- Column: 30 m x 250 µm id x 0.25 µm HP-5MS
- Injection: Spitless, 250 °C, 25 µL injection volume
- Carrier: Helium (approximately 65 kPa) (9.43 psi),

constant pressure

- Oven program: 40 to 240 °C at 20 °C/min (30 min analysis times)
- Detection: MS in scan mode (40-400 amu); solvent delay: 3 min; transfer line: 280 °C

D. Identification of Volatile Components

The identification of volatile compounds was performed by their mass spectra with data from Adam, the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) mass spectra library.

E. Statistical Analysis

Data obtained were analyzed using the GraphPad Prism 5 version 5.01 (GraphPad Software Inc. La Jolla, CA. USA). All values are expressed as mean±standard deviation for three replicates. Data were analyzed by ANOVA and the statistical significance differences were analyzed using the paired t-test; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The volatile components of Pang-Rum were identified by the retention times of the GC-MS analysis. The six peak area components of the oil and percentage of each constituent were summarized and presented in Table I.

Analysis of the isolate by GC-MS resulted in the identification of six components comprising 100% of total volatile components. The chromatogram of Pang-Rum was detected by mass spectrum in scan mode (40-400 amu). For six peak the presence of Camphene (27.6%), D-Limonene (40.5%), Phenylethyl Alcohol (88.4%), endo-Borneol (39.5%), 6-Octen-1-ol,3,7-dimethyl-,(R)- (38%), and Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-,(1S)- (23.4%), were also detected, as shown in Table II.

The chromatogram of Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder was detected by mass spectrum in scan mode (40-400 amu). The compounds of Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder by GC-MS were compared with the NIST library and shown in Table III.

The stabilities of the essential oils from Pang-Rum and Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder were evaluated by GC-MS. The compounds found in Pang-Rum stored at room temperature for six months were identified as: Phenylethyl Alcohol (57.6%), Camphene (13.2%), endo-Borneol (17.6%), Citronellol (13.8%), and Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-,(1S)- (17.5%), as shown in Table IV.

Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder was stored at room temperature for six months. The compounds identified, shown in Table V include, Phenylethyl Alcohol (85.6%), Camphene (13.4%), endo-Borneol (27.7%), Citronellol (21.3%), and Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-,(1S)- (21.4%).

The analysis of Pang-Rum stored at 45°C for six months, five peaks of compounds were identified as: Phenylethyl Alcohol (61.5%), Camphene (14.7%), Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol,1,7,7-trimethyl-,formate,endo-(16.8%), Citronellol (21.3%), and Bicyclo[3.1.1] heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-,(1S)- (14.7%), as shown in Table VI.

Table VII shows the components identified of Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder at 45°C for six months, five peaks of compounds were identified as; Phenylethyl Alcohol (62.4%) Camphene (14.2%), Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol,1,7,7-trimethyl-, formate, endo- (15.6%), Citronellol (13.2%), and Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane, 6,6- dimethyl-2-methylene-,(1S)- (21.4%).

TABLE I
AVERAGE OF MAIN RETENTION TIME AND TOTAL AREA PEAK OF ESSENTIAL OILS FROM PANG-RUM WITH/WITHOUT BINDER

Formula	RT	% of area peak				% Total of area peak
		0	1	3	6	
Pang-Rum	7.553	3.26	2.07	1.16	1.09	97.59
	10.236	16.53	11.66	15.78	5.64	
	10.968	26.66	20.30	20.95	27.29	
	11.112	41.83	49.64	50.21	55.47	
	11.917	6.00	9.60	8.05	7.19	
	12.302	2.49	5.74	3.85	2.87	
Pang-Rum with binder	7.553	2.09	1.69	0	4.31	97.50
	10.236	17.74	20.63	12.88	13.18	
	10.968	20.86	16.81	21.17	26.71	
	11.112	45.34	43.63	50.24	46.86	
	11.917	7.46	10.17	10.19	4.85	
	12.302	4.13	4.69	4.26	2.14	

RT=retention time

TABLE II
COMPOUNDS OF PANG-RUM BY GC-MS COMPARED WITH NIST LIBRARY

Peak	RT	Compound	MF	MW	%Prop
1	7.543	Camphene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	27.6
2	8.870	D-Limonene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	40.5
3	10.253	Phenylethyl Alcohol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	122	88.4
4	11.120	endo-Borneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154	39.5
5	11.922	6-Octen-1-ol, 3,7-dimethyl-, (R)-	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	38.0
6	12.308	Bicyclo[3.1.1] heptane, 6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	23.4

RT=retention time, MF=molecular formula, MW=molecular weight, %Prop= property percentage

TABLE III
COMPOUNDS OF PANG-RUM WITH 10%W/W BINDER BY GC-MS COMPARED WITH NIST LIBRARY

Peak	RT	Compound	MF	MW	%Prop
1	7.526	Camphene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	29.6
2	8.879	D-Limonene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	25.2
3	10.253	Phenylethyl Alcohol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	122	88.4
4	10981	Isobornyl formate	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O ₂	182	19.2
5	11.125	endo-Borneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154	39.3
6	11.927	6-Octen-1-ol, 3,7-dimethyl-, (R)-	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	38.7
7	12.308	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane, 6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	23.7

RT=retention time, MF=molecular formula, MW=molecular weight, %Prop= property percentage

TABLE IV

COMPOUNDS OF PANG-RUM STORED AT ROOM TEMPERATURE FOR 6 MONTHS

Peak	RT	Compound	MF	MW	%Prop
1	10.236	Phenylethyl Alcohol	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	122	57.6
2	10.968	Camphene	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	136	13.2
3	11.116	endo-Borneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154	17.6
4	11.918	Citronellol	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	13.8
5	12.299	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	17.5

RT=retention time, MF=molecular formula, MW=molecular weight, %Prop= property percentage

TABLE V

COMPOUNDS OF PANG-RUM WITH 10%w/w BINDER STORED AT ROOM TEMPERATURE FOR 6 MONTHS

Peak	RT	Compound	MF	MW	%Prop
1	10.231	Phenylethyl Alcohol	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	122	85.6
2	10.968	Camphene	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	136	13.4
3	11.109	endo-Borneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154	27.7
4	11.914	Citronellol	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	21.3
5	12.299	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	21.4

RT=retention time, MF=molecular formula, MW=molecular weight, %Prop= property percentage

TABLE VI

COMPOUNDS OF PANG-RUM STORED AT 45°C FOR 6 MONTHS

Peak	RT	Compound	MF	MW	%Prop
1	10.236	Phenylethyl Alcohol	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	122	61.5
2	10.968	Camphene	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	136	14.7
3	11.116	Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol, 1,7,7-trimethyl-, formate, endo	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₂	182	16.8
4	11.913	Citronellol	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	12.3
5	12.299	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	14.7

RT=retention time, MF=molecular formula, MW=molecular weight, %Prop= property percentage

TABLE VII

COMPOUNDS OF PANG-RUM WITH 10%w/w BINDER STORED AT 45°C FOR 6 MONTH

Peak	RT	Compound	MF	MW	%Prop
1	10.236	Phenylethyl Alcohol	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	122	62.4
2	10.964	Camphene	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	136	14.2
3	11.111	Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol, 1,7,7-trimethyl-, formate, endo	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₂	182	15.6
4	11.918	Citronellol	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	156	13.2
5	12.304	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane,6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136	21.4

RT=retention time, MF=molecular formula, MW=molecular weight, %Prop= property percentage

Fig. 2 Stability of essential oils from Pang-Rum with/without binder (at least 6 months)

Fig. 2 shows the percentage of total peak area of Pang-Rum with/without binder stored at room temperature and 45°C for six months. The results found that the stability of essential oil from Pang-Rum with/without binder were not significant. Pang-Rum and Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder presented similar major compounds from seven chromatograms. For the six month samples, the components of Pang-Rum and Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder showed change. Meanwhile, the compounds of Pang-Rum and Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder were similar in all conditions (room temperature and 45°C). But some components of Pang-Rum and compounds of Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder were found to be different in the comparison of the room temperature and 45°C samples.

Both of the different Pang-Ram mass spectrum (Pang-Ram and Pang-Rum with 10%w/w binder) showed isomer compounds as 6-Octen-1-ol,3,7- dimethyl-,(R)- and Citronellol when compared with day zero (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Components of Pang-Rum with/without binder are isomer; A) components of Pang-Rum with/without binder for 0 day, B) components of Pang-Rum with/without binder for 6 months

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results show that the essential oil content and quality of Pang-Rum without binder and Pang-Rum with binder were similar all conditions. Following from [7], future

research will study the essential oil content and quality of essential oil at 4 °C and -20 °C.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest with this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Gupta, D. Prakash, and S. Gupta, "A biotechnological approach to microbial based perfumes and flavours," *Journal of Microbiology & Experimentation*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp.1-89, 2015.
- [2] C. H. V. Fidelisa, F. Augustoa, P. T. B. Sampaio, P. M. Krainovic, and L. E. S. Baratac, "Chemical characterization of rosewood (*Aniba rosaodora* Ducke) leaf essential oil by comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography coupled with quadrupole mass spectrometry," *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, vol. 24, no 3, pp.245-251, 2012.
- [3] A. Chiabchalard and N. Nooron, "Antihyperglycemic effects of *Pandanus amaryllifolius* Roxb. leaf extract," *Pharmacognosy Magazine*, vol. 11, no. 41, pp.117-122, 2015.
- [4] N. E. Klinjumpa, "Thai Flavours and Fragrances for Thai wisdom" Bangkok: Se-education, pp. 76-81, 2002.
- [5] M. Pael, V. Radulescu, and D. C. Ilies, "GC-MS analysis of essential oil obtained from the species *Thymus comosus* Heuff. ex Griseb. (Lamiaceae)," *Farmacia*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp.479-484.
- [6] D. J. Daferera, B. N. Ziogas, and M. G. Polissiou, "GC-MS analysis of essential oils from some Greek aromatic plants and their fungitoxicity on *Penicillium digitatum*," *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp.2576-2581, 2000.
- [7] S. Sharma, and R. Kumar, "Effect of temperature and storage duration of flowers on essential oil content and composition of damask rose (*Rosa × damascena* Mill.) under western Himalayas," *Journal of Applied Research on Medicinal and Aromatic Plants*, vol. 3, pp.10-17, 2016.

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